

TURKISTONLIK GENERAL AYOL, MILLAT ONASI-QURBONJON DODXOHNING MARD, JASUR VA VATANPARVARLIGI HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada chor Rossiyasining mustamlakachilik zulmiga qarshi ko'tarilgan xalq qo'zg'olonida Olay vohasi hokimi, Olay malikasi sifatida mashhur bo'lgan Kurbonjon dodxohning olib botgan mardonavor kurashi, besh nafar o'gillarining Vatan ozodligi yolida mardlarcha vafot etishi, uning ibratli hayoti haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Olay vohasi, Qo'qon xonligi, mustamlakachilik, Chor Rossiyasi, Turkiston general gubernatori.

ABOUT THE BRAVE, COURAGEOUS AND PATRIOTISM OF KURBONJON DODKOH, WOMAN GENERAL FROM TURKEY, MOTHER OF THE NATION

Abstract. This article talks about the heroic struggle of Kurbanjon Dodkhoh, known as the governor of the Olay oasis and the Queen of Olay, in the people's uprising against the colonial oppression of Tsarist Russia, the heroic death of her five sons for the freedom of the Motherland, and her exemplary life.

Key words: Olai oasis, Kokhan Khanate, colonialism, Tsarist Russia, Governor General of Turkestan.

О ХРАБРОМ, МУЖЕСТВЕННОМ И ПАТРИОТИЗМЕ КУРБОНДЖОН ДОДКО, ЖЕНЩИНЕ-ГЕНЕРАЛУ ИЗ ТУРЦИИ, МАТЕРИ НАЦИИ

Аннотация. Статья сказано о доблестной борьбе Курбанджон Додхох, известной как правительница Олайского оазиса и царица Олая, в народном восстании против колониального гнета царской России, героической гибели ее пятерых сыновей за свободу Родины и ее образцовая жизнь.

Ключевые слова: оазис Олай, Коканское ханство, колониализм, Императорская Россия, Туркестанский генерал-губернатор.

Qurbonjon dodxoh qo'zg'oloni — chor Rossiyasining mustamlakachilik zulmiga qarshi ko'tarilgan xalq qo'zg'olonida Olay vohasi hokimi, Olay malikasi sifatida mashhur bo'lgan Kurbonjon dodxoh boshchilik qilgan.

Kurmanjon (Qurbonjon) dodxoh 1811-yili Qo‘qon xonligiga qarashli O‘sh shahri yaqinida Mungush qabilasidagi oddiy ko‘chmanchi oilada tavallud topdi. Uning bolalik va o‘smirlik yillari haqida ma‘lumotlar juda kam, deyarli yo‘q desa ham bo‘ladi. Qurbonjon Mamatqizi Qo‘qon xonligi vaziri Olimbek dodxoh Hasanboy o‘g‘lining rafiqasi bo‘lgan. Umr yo‘ldoshi uni xon saroyiga olib kelib, Nodirabegimga tanishtiradi. Nodirabegim va Uvaysiy kabi o‘zbek shoiralari ta‘sirida Qurbonjonning dunyoqarashi shakllanadi.

Qo‘qon xonligi dodxohi Olimbekning nikohidan besh o‘g‘il: Abdullabek, Mamitbek, Asanbek, Botirbek va Qamchibek dunyoga keladi. Ularning bari kelgusida bosqinchilarga qarshi janglarda qatnashadi. Tarixchi V.P.Nalivkinning yozishicha, Olimbek Andijon viloyati hokimi bo‘lgan. Bu vaqtda ruslar birin-ketin xonlik shaharlarini egallab kelayotgan edi. 1860-yili Mallaxon ularga qarshi lashkar yuboradi va Olimbek ham qirg‘izlarga bosh bo‘lib jangga ketadi. Ammo qattiq qish sabab qo‘shin talafotga uchraydi. Keyingi yilgi yurishda esa Olimbek qatnashishdan bosh tortadi. Bunga javoban Mallaxon uni qo‘lga olishni buyuradi. Olimbek G‘ulchaga chekinishga muvaffaq bo‘ladi. Ammo uning mol-mulki tortib olinadi. 1862-yili saroydagi o‘yinlar oqibatida tuzoqqa tushirilib, o‘ldiriladi. Kurmanjon esa beva bo‘lib qoladi. Bu vaqtda Buxoro amiri Sayyid Muzaffar Xudoyorxonga yordam berish uchun Qo‘qonga qo‘shin tortib keladi. O‘sh shahrida Kurmanjon bilan tanishib, uning qirg‘izlar orasidagi nufuzini ko‘rgach, dodxoh unvonini beradi. Olimbekning vorisi hisoblangan to‘ng‘ich o‘g‘li Jarqinboy o‘gay onasining foydasiga lavozimdan chekinadi. Shundan keyin qirg‘izlar boshqaruvi Kurmanjon qo‘liga o‘tadi. Jarqinboy esa 1864-yili O‘shga hokim etib tayinlanadi. Ammo ruslarga qarshi janglardan birida vafot etadi. Shunday bir davrda Xudoyorxon Qo‘qon taxtiga o‘tiradi va Kurmanjon dodxoh uning huzuriga kelganda dodxoh lavozimini tasdiqlab beradi.

To‘ng‘ich o‘g‘li Abdullabek esa Jarqinboy o‘rniga O‘shga hokim bo‘ladi.

Zamondoshlarining fikricha, Kurmanjon dodxoh boshqaruvni oqillik bilan olib borgan va uning dovrug‘i Qo‘qon tashqarisiga ham yoyilgan. Buxoro, Qashqar amir va xonlari alohida ehtirom ko‘rsatib, turli sovg‘a-salomlar yuborib turgan. Oloyga safar qilgan rus olimi Fedchenko barcha qirg‘izlar unga yuksak hurmat bildirishini, yuqori mulozamat bilan murojaat qilishini yozib qoldirgan. Dodxohning tashqi ko‘rinishi haqida deyarli ma‘lumotlar saqlanmagan. Rossiya armiyasi ofitseri Boris Tageyev uning Skobelev bilan suhbatida ishtirok etgan va shunday ta‘riflagan: “Bo‘yi uncha baland emas, yoshi katta bo‘lishiga qaramasdan, go‘zal ayol, mo‘yna bilan bezatilgan broker xalat kiyib olgan”.

Tashqi siyosat bobida ham Qurbonjon dodxoh anchayin iste‘dod sohibasi sifatida tanilgan.

Xususan, Qashqardagi Yettishahar uyg‘ur davlati hukumdori Yoqubbek bilan yaxshi qo‘shnichilik munosabatlarini o‘rnatgan. Qalqib turgan zamon, Chor Rossiyasi mustamlakachilik

siyosati va xonlikdagi chirish Oloy malikasini ham qo'lga qurol tutishga majbur etgandi. "Po'latxon" qo'zg'oloni maqomida tarixga muhrlangan tengsiz mahorabaga Qurbonjon dodxoh ham qo'shiladi

Kurmanjon dodxohning Qo'qon xonligidagi faoliyati 1976-yilgacha, ya'ni Qo'qon xonligining Rossiya imperiyasi tomonidan anneksiya qilinishi va xonlikning tugatilishigacha davom etdi. Biroq qirg'izlar bo'ysunishdan bosh tortdi va tog'larga chekinib qarshilik ko'rsatish harakatini boshladi. Ularga Kurmanjon dodxoh va o'g'illari yetakchilik qildi. 1,5 ming qirg'iz yigitlari dodxoh o'g'illari boshchiligida Oloy tog'laridagi qishloqlarga joylashdi. 1876-yil 25-aprel kuni ikki tomon o'rtasida ilk jiddiy to'qnashuv yuz berdi. Bir kun davom etgan jangda ruslar qirg'izlarni o'z pozitsiyalaridan chiqarib yuborishga va katta yo'qotishlarga uchratishga erishdi.

Turkiston general gubernatori Fon Kaufman Oloy vohasidagi qo'zg'olonni bostirishga shafqatsizligi bilan dong chiqargan general Skobelevni yo'llaydi. Qariyb bir yil davom etgan urushdan bosqinchi armiya jiddiy talofat ko'radi. Qurbonjon dodxoh va uning farzandlari bosqinchilarga qarshi ayovsiz kurashgan. Kuchlar teng kelmasligi "ajdahoni" yengish mushkul ekanligini tushungan holda maydonni tark etmagan. Oxir oqibatda Farg'ona viloyati harbiy gubernatori Skobelev O'sh uezdi hokimi P. P. Ionov vositachiligida Qurbonjon dodxoh bilan aloqa bog'lagan. General va Oloy malikasining yuzma-yuz uchrashuvida tinchlik sulhi tuziladi.

Qurbonjon dodxohning o'g'illari Mahmudbek, Hasanbek, Botirbek Kobuldagi quvg'inlikdan chaqirilib, ularga Oloy vohasida yangi tuzilgan bo'lislarga boshchilik qilish topshirilgan. Uning kichik o'g'li Qamchibek esa keyinchalik rus ma'murlari tomonidan O'shda dorga osib o'ldirilgan. *Nurilla Shamsiev o'zining "ОЛОЙ МАЛИКАСИ"* maqolasida shunday tasvirlagan: O'sh shahri. Chor Rossiyasi mustamlakachilari tomonidan jazo hukmi ijro etiladigan qatl maydoniga yog'iy tazyiqi ostida har galgidanda ko'proq olomon yig'ilgan. Bosqinchilar Oloy malikasi deya e'zoz etilgan Qurbonjon dodxohning kenja o'g'li Qamchibekni osib o'ldirishga hukm etgan. Barcha vahimada, barchaning nigohi dor ostidagi yosh yigitda.

Dushmanlarga aynan shu kerak. Ya'ni mustamlakachilarga qarshi isyon ko'tarishning oqibati shafqatsiz bo'lishini, ularga qarshi kurashish befoyda va dahshatli ekanini ko'rsatish.

Bosqinchilarning rejasi faqat bu emas. Yengilmas isyonchilarning boshlig'i – Qurbonjon dodxohni shu orqali qo'lga olish. Jonfido ona, albatta, bolasi bilan vidolashish uchun kelishi tayin.

Maydon atrofidagi va xalq orasidagi dushman ayg'oqchilari bu borada hushyor. Oloy malikasi ham buni yaxshi biladi.

Shu payt uzoqdan chang ko'tarilib, bir otliq – Qurbonjon momo uchib kela boshladi. U nafasi ichiga tushgan olomonni yorib o'tib, to'g'ri dor ostiga keldi. Bolasiga yuzlanib: «O'g'lim, dadil bo'l. Yurt uchun shahid ketish bizga merosdir, sendan roziman», dedi-yu, ot jilovini ortga

burdi-da, qanday kelgan bo'lsa, maydonni shiddat ila shunday tark etdi. Dushman, hatto chora ko'rishga imkon topa olmadi...

Qurbonjon dodxoh! Yurt ozodligi, xalq dardi yetti farzandning onasi bo'lgan bu ayolni jangchi suvvoraga aylantirgan bo'lsa, ajabmas. Oloy malikasi deya nom olgan bu zabardast ayol haqida qo'shiqlar, rivoyatlar to'qilgan. Negaki, xalq o'z qahramonlarini hamisha e'zozlaydi, ulug'laydi, unutmaydi. Uning mo''tabar nomi hamon asrlarni ortda qoldirib kelmoqda.

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